

Evaluation of the Reduction of Lesson Hours in Public Schools According to the Views of Teachers at All Levels

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Abstract

The aim of the study is to evaluate the reduction of course hours in the 2024-2025 academic year in the province of Istanbul according to the opinions of teachers working at primary, secondary and high school level and in different branches. In the research, answers to research questions such as ‘What should be considered when determining the course hours?’, ‘What are the effects of reducing the course hours on the strategies, methods and techniques used in the lesson?’, ‘What are the situations experienced with the reduction of the course hours to 35 minutes?’ were sought in the research. The study group was formed by maximum diversity sampling method. The study group consists of teachers working in 2 primary schools, 2 secondary schools and 2 high schools in Sultanbeyli district of Istanbul province. Thirty-five people from 11 different branches participated in the study. In this study, which was conducted with qualitative research method, ‘case study’, one of the qualitative research designs, was applied. A structured interview form consisting of ten questions developed by the researcher was used as a data collection tool. In the presentation of the data, the forms were evaluated by content analysis method, five categories were determined according to the interview questions and coding was done. In order to ensure the internal validity of the research, the form was prepared in accordance with the scientific process, pre-evaluated and approved by experts in the field. In order to ensure internal reliability, the codes related to teachers' views on the reduction of course hours were supported by direct quotations. In order to ensure external reliability and validity, the research method and research process were explained in detail. According to the data obtained in the study, most of the teachers stated that the reduction of course hours was compatible with the simplified education programme within the scope of the education model, that it increased the attitude and motivation of students towards school and that they did not have any difficulty in completing the annual programme. In addition, they also added that the reduction of the course duration affected the methods and techniques they used in their lessons and that in some branches they could not complete the subjects in the specified time. As a result of the research, the majority of the teachers stated that the course duration should continue to be 35 minutes.

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INTRODUCTION

When we look at the education programs implemented from the past to the present, we see that the ultimate goal is to develop the individual to be educated cognitively, affective or physically in the direction we expect from the program. Since the needs of the individual or society differ according to the conditions of the time, it has been inevitable for education to adapt to changing conditions and change accordingly. Today's education program has adopted the constructivist education approach that puts the individual at the center and attaches importance to individual differences. With the adoption of this approach, it has become obligatory to take the characteristics of the individual as a basis when preparing education programs. Today, lessons at all levels in schools are determined as 40 minutes and when the attention span of the individual is considered, many factors such as age, gender, perception level, health status, readiness level are also effective on the attention span, so there are problem situations such as the appropriateness of the determined time or the need to change it. In all districts of Istanbul province, for the 2024-2025 academic year, class hours were reduced to 35 minutes with the decision of the governorate in schools with dual education at all levels, and the reflections of this situation on education were inevitable.

The expected and desired situation when creating education systems and accordingly designing the program is to observe the desired behavioral change at the end of the allotted time. We call this behavioral change success. Success is actually a person's evaluation of the distance he/she has traveled from the point where he/she started his/her life to the point where he/she has arrived, and his/her way of looking at this process (Özkan & Gündüz, 2008). The success of the mass or individual to whom the program is applied also means the success of the program, and the main goal of the program changes made in our education system is success. It is desired to bring the individual, society, country's economy, cultural values, living standards, health level to the best level in a positive sense, and these are only dependent on the success of the programs. The vast majority of educational activities take place in classrooms, so in order to increase success; many issues such as methods and techniques applied in the classroom, teacher competencies, student readiness, consideration of individual differences, reflections of environmental factors in the classroom, time management are important. Among these variables, time management is emphasized today.

In recent years, the Ministry of National Education has been making efforts to move away from the practice of dual education and switch all schools to full day. The common conclusion in most of the literature reviews on dual education is that dual education is disadvantageous for students. Aktay et al. (2019) argued that dual education is disadvantageous for students due to issues such as students going to school too early in the morning or leaving school too late, creating sleep problems in the morning, or students having difficulty getting to and from school in adverse weather conditions. Camuzcu (2007), on the other hand, emphasized that students at the same level who are subject to full-day education have an advantage over students who are subject to dual education. In the 2024-2025 academic year in Istanbul, in primary, secondary and high schools with dual education, class hours were reduced to 35 minutes with the decision of the governorate in 34 districts due to the fact that situations such as coming to school very early in the morning and leaving school very late in the evening jeopardized student safety. In terms of the number of classes, this means that each student spends at least half an hour less time in the classroom each day. Schools increased students' rest time by spreading some of this reduced time over breaks. Issues such as reducing the amount of time students spend in school and reducing the number of class hours have been discussed in education policy and the concept of time management has been particularly encountered in these discussions. Such discussions have led to a focus on issues such as whether class times are sufficient or not, and how much class time should be allocated (Gall, Gall, Jacobsen, & Bullock, 1990). With this system in practice, these issues will be evaluated.

In Turkey, a 40-minute class hour is used in primary, middle and high school programs. In the 2023-2024 academic year, in the schools affiliated to the General Directorate of Vocational and

Technical Education, due to the increase in the number of students due to the increase in the number of students moving to another school or moving to their own school within the scope of demolition and construction or retrofitting, the lessons were reduced from 40 minutes to 30 minutes in the schools within the scope. However, apart from this, there has not been any change in lesson hours in our country. When we look at the course hours in different countries, we see that in Germany primary school classes are 45 minutes, in Finland they are 45 minutes, in France they are 60 minutes in primary schools and 55 minutes in secondary education, and in Japan each class is 45 minutes long. In the UK, on the other hand, each school has the authority to organize the curriculum differently and a lesson hour is 35, 40, 45, 55 or 60 minutes.

From the 1926 primary school program to the present day, it can be said that the duration of lessons has not changed, while the number of weekly lesson hours has increased. In the 1926, 1936, 1948 and 1962 draft programs, there were 26 weekly lessons in primary school, while in the 1968 program it was reduced to 25, and in the 2000 and 2005 programs it was increased to 30 hours (Tazebay et al., 2000; Vural, 2000, 2008). In the 2000 and 2005 programs, the number of courses was increased to 30 with elective courses, which were 3 hours for fifth grades in the 2000 program and 2 hours for first, second, third, fourth and fifth grades in the 2005 program (Vural, 2000, 2008). In addition, according to the weekly course schedule of primary education institutions published by the Board of Education, which is valid as of the 2023-2024 academic year, 30 lesson hours have been reached with free activity hours. According to the same schedule, the weekly total of common and elective courses is 35 hours in secondary schools, 36 hours in imam hatip secondary schools, 40 hours in sports high schools, 43 hours in fine arts high schools and 40 hours in other secondary education institutions.

When the education systems of other countries are analyzed, it is observed that the number of weekly courses is lower than in Turkey. According to Arı (2004) and Sağlam (1999), for primary schools, it is 28 in Belgium, 26-27 in France, 25-31 in Portugal, 17-27 in Germany, 30 in Luxembourg, 22 in the Netherlands, 21-25 in Austria. At the secondary school level, it is 30-32 hours in Germany, 32-34 hours in Austria and 25 hours in the Netherlands.

When the annual time allocated to teaching within the scope of compulsory education is analyzed, it is found that at the primary school level, the average teaching time is 799 hours in OECD countries, 775 hours in EU-22 countries and 720 hours in Turkey. At the secondary school level, this period is 915 hours in OECD countries, 895 hours in EU-22 countries and 843 hours in Turkey (OECD, 2016a). These data show that Turkey lags behind OECD and EU-22 countries in terms of the time allocated to teaching at both primary and secondary school levels. It is noteworthy, however, that more instructional time does not directly guarantee academic success. For example, countries such as Germany, Finland and South Korea have relatively less instructional time, yet they achieve higher results in international exams (OECD, 2016b). This situation reveals that the quality of teaching, the effectiveness of the strategies and methods used, and the school climate are more determinative than time. In this context, the reduction of class hours in Istanbul in the 2024-2025 academic year is meaningful both in terms of Turkey's overall education time table and international comparisons. Questions such as how the reduction of class hours to 35 minutes is reflected on the teaching process, the strategies, methods and techniques used by teachers, and how this change is evaluated by teachers are important for understanding the effectiveness of current educational policies. For this reason, it is seen that how the time spent in the classroom is used and how much of it is allocated to education is more important than the quantitative value of the time students spend in the classroom. According to international studies, when we look at the activities and practices carried out in the classroom in a lesson hour, it is seen that the time allocated to teaching is very little in the lesson hour. According to a study conducted by the World Bank, the proportion of time allocated to teaching in a lesson hour is 79% in Tunisia, 63% in Brazil and 39% in Ghana (Abadzi, 2007). Based on these data, in the 2023 education vision document, the Ministry of National Education (MoNE, 2018) emphasized how to use the time in the classroom or during the lesson with the statement 'By reducing compulsory course

hours and types at all levels, the necessary time will be provided for in-depth study, practice and personalization in basic courses. In addition, according to the results of the "40 minutes lecture, 40 minutes break" project implemented in 14 pilot schools in Antalya and the results of the research conducted on secondary education students, the item that students most wanted to be implemented among the goals of the "2023 Education Vision" was "reducing compulsory class hours" (Usul, 2019).

There are different opinions among educators and researchers about the time allocated for teaching. According to Gökçe (2012), the time allocated for teaching should be increased for reasons such as teachers' preparation and planning for the lesson, preparing different learning environments for students with different learning styles, implementing the curriculum in detail, and having students who require more time and effort for learning in the classroom environment. According to researchers and educators with different views, as the time spent at school increases, students' participation in out-of-school activities is negatively affected, teachers demand additional fees, and resource limitations and cost burden occur (Çaycı, 2018).

Purpose of the Study

The aim of the study is to evaluate the issue of changing the course hours, which has been a subject of debate in our country for many years, according to the opinions of teachers from different branches working in schools where the course hours were reduced to 35 minutes this year.

Importance of the Study

The importance of the research is to shed light on the issue of changing the course hours with this system that is currently being implemented for educators, researchers and educational planners.

METHOD

In this section, the research method, study group, data collection tool, data collection and data analysis are explained. The research questions are given below.

1. What should be considered when determining lesson hours?
2. What is the effect of reducing lesson hours on the strategies, methods and techniques used in the lesson?
3. What would be the effect of reducing lesson hours on students' cognitive, affective and psychomotor behaviors?
4. What are the situations experienced with the reduction of class hours to 35 minutes?
5. What kind of a change should be made in course hours?

Within the scope of this study, ethics committee permission was granted on 09.01.2025 with the number E-61923333-050.99-436948. decision was taken from Sakarya University Ethics Committee.

Methodology of the Study

The method of the research is 'case study', which is one of the qualitative research designs. According to Yıldırım and Şimşek (2006), case study design is a research design that enables the examination of a phenomenon and event that is not under the control of the researcher in all its details and whose basic questions are how and why. In this study, a case study was used because 35 minutes was not practiced in all schools in Istanbul; it was practiced in 34 districts and only in schools with dual education.

Study Group

The study group was determined by maximum diversity sampling method, which is one of the purposeful sampling methods. The aim of this method is to create a small sample and reflect the views

of the participants to the maximum extent. For this reason, it was ensured that teachers working in different branches contributed to the research as much as possible. The study group consists of teachers from 11 different branches working in the province of Istanbul . 35 teachers participated in the study, 19 of them were female and 16 of them were male. According to the years of service, 22,86% of the teachers have 0-5 years of service, 42,86% have 6-10 years of service, 28,57% have 11-20 years of service and 5,71% have 21 years or more of service. When we look at the age of the teachers; 37,14% of them are between 20-30 years old, 42,86% between 31-40 years old, and 20% between 41-50 years old. The study group was selected from 6 different schools, 2 of which were primary schools, 2 were secondary schools and 2 were Anatolian high schools. Since the application was not applied to all schools in Istanbul, but only to all schools that had to do dual education due to overcrowding, schools that had to do dual education due to overcrowding in Sultanbeyli district were selected and schools from all levels were determined for the consistency of the sample. The table below shows the distribution of the teachers in the research group according to their branches.

Table 1. Distribution of teachers according to their branches

<i>Teaching Subject</i>	<i>Teacher's Code</i>	<i>Count</i>
Classroom Teacher	Ö1,Ö3,Ö6,Ö8,Ö10,Ö11,Ö12,Ö15,Ö16,Ö19,Ö20,Ö22,Ö25,Ö26	14
Maths Teacher	Ö13,Ö24,Ö29,Ö31,Ö32	5
Religious Culture and Moral Knowledge Teacher	Ö5,Ö28,Ö35	3
Turkish Teacher	Ö17,Ö18,Ö23	3
Science Teacher	Ö2,Ö27	2
History Teacher	Ö4,Ö34	2
Turkish Language and Literature Teacher	Ö7,Ö14	2
Physical Education Teacher	Ö33	1
English Teacher	Ö21	1
Music Teacher	Ö9	1
Social Studies Teacher	Ö30	1
TOTAL		35

Data Collection Tool

In this study, data were collected in writing through structured interview forms. The interview questions varied and changed according to the answers given. The research questions consist of two parts. In the first part, the personal information of the participants was tried to be obtained. In the second part, the opinions of the study group on the evaluation of the duration of the lesson hours were tried to be obtained. The studies on this subject in the literature and the opinions of academicians were important factors in the formulation of the interview questions. After the interview questions were created, interview forms were distributed to a small group of teachers and examined. After the pre-interview, it was observed that the questions were understood and there were no identical or similar answers to different questions. In addition, the interview form was discussed with two different faculty members who are experts in the field and approved by them. The interview form used in the study is given in Appendix 1.

Data Collection and Analysis

Data collection started on December 17, 2024 and ended on December 24, 2024. For the purpose of data collection, the researcher informed the teachers she knew and could reach about the research and encouraged them to participate in the research. The data collection process was

terminated after the same data was repeated and saturation was reached; the forms that did not meet the desired criteria were eliminated and the data were finalized.

A total of 35 forms were analyzed as a whole. No qualitative data analysis software was used in this process. In addition, the data were analyzed by content analysis method. What is done in content analysis is to collect opinions close to each other under certain categories/themes, to support them with participant opinion and frequency, and to tabulate and interpret them in a language that the reader can understand. For this reason, the analysis process consists of preliminary preparation, coding, reaching categories, organizing, interpreting and reporting, and supporting with participant opinions. The code table explaining the codes determined in the tabulation of the categories is given below.

Table 2. Code Table

<i>Codes</i>	<i>Definition</i>	<i>Category</i>
Caution	Attention span depending on the age of the student	1
Programme	Intensity of the curriculum	1
School hours	School entry and exit times	1
Form of education	Single education-dual education status	1
Caution	Attention and perception are opened	3
Interest	Increased interest and motivation towards the lesson	3
Concern	Concern about understanding the subject	3
Learning difficulties	Makes learning more difficult	3
Fatigue	Reduced physical fatigue	3
Focusing	Increased focus and attention span	4
Motivation	Increase in teacher motivation	4
Out of school time	Increased out-of-school time for students	4
Interest	Increased interest in the course	4
Watches	School entrance and exit times	4
Training programme	Suitable for the simplified education programme	4
Programme	Intensity of the curriculum	4

Validity - Reliability

In order to ensure the internal validity of the study, the form created as a data collection tool was prepared in accordance with the principles of qualitative research; it was subjected to a preliminary evaluation before being submitted to expert opinion. Then, the form was examined by two faculty members who are experts in their fields in terms of content validity and approved by making the necessary arrangements. This process supports the extent to which the data obtained overlap with the research purpose and the validity of the concepts measured. Within the scope of internal reliability, the codes obtained from the teachers' views on the reduction of course hours were supported by direct participant quotations. In this way, deviations that may arise from the subjectivity of the comments were reduced and the transparency of the data was increased. The participants were coded sequentially as T1, T2, T3... and the quotations were presented in relation to these codes. In addition, the coding process was carried out independently by two different graduate students other than the researcher and the same themes were reached, which showed the consistency of the analysis process. This method is based on inter-rater comparison, which is one of the frequently used reliability

enhancement techniques in qualitative research. For external validity and external reliability, the research method, research design, participant characteristics, data collection process and data analysis stages were described in detail. In this way, it was possible to make comparisons with other studies to be conducted in similar contexts, and the generalizability of the results and the reproducibility of the study were supported. In particular, the clarity regarding the process of creating and verifying themes reinforces the scientific reliability of the study. In accordance with qualitative research standards, obtaining expert opinion to ensure the reliability of the themes obtained and ensuring consistency between coders during the analysis process increase the methodological robustness of the research.

FINDINGS

The data obtained from the interview forms applied in the research were coded and 5 categories were formed. Under each heading, codes, participants, frequency values and quotations were analyzed separately.

In Table 3, 'What should be considered when determining the course hours' is analyzed.

Table 3. Category-1 What should be considered when determining the course hours?

<i>Codes</i>	<i>Participants-Frequency</i>	<i>Quote</i>
Caution	Ö5,6,8,11,12,13,14,15,16,20,22, 23 24,25,26,28,29,30,31,32,34,35 (22)	Ö22- <i>“The attention span of the students should be taken into consideration due to their age.”</i>
Programme	Ö2,5,6,9,15,18,20,21,23,24,27,32 (12)	Ö9- <i>“Course hours should be determined taking into account the intensity of the training programme.”</i>
School hours	Ö1,4,8,13,17,19,33 (7)	Ö13- <i>“Morning and evening entry and exit times should not be too early or late.”</i>
Form of education	Ö3,10,12,28,29 (5)	Ö29- <i>“It should be taken into consideration whether the school is single or dual education.”</i>
Transport facilities	Ö7,8,19 (3)	Ö8- <i>“The location of the province/district/village and transport situation should be taken into consideration.”</i>

When the opinions of the teachers participating in the research are analyzed, it is understood that the attention span depending on the age of the student should be taken into consideration in determining the course hours. Afterwards, the majority of the teachers said that lesson hours should be determined according to the intensity of the curriculum. It was emphasized that school entry and exit times should be taken into consideration, dual or single education and transportation facilities should be taken into consideration.

In Table 4, 'The effect of reducing lesson hours on the strategies, methods and techniques used in the lesson' is analyzed.

Table 4. The Effect of Reducing Category-2 Lesson Hours on the Strategies, Methods and Techniques Used in the Lesson

Codes	Participants-Frequency	Quote
Does Not Affect	Ö1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,18,22,29,30,32,33,35 (22)	Ö2- "I continue to use methods and techniques such as experiment, group work, simulation, drama, etc. The reduction of class hours did not change my teaching."
Influencing	Ö9,17,19,20,21,23,24,25,26,27,28,31,34 (13)	Ö34- "Yes, it does. I cannot explain the subjects in detail, I cannot answer students' questions in detail, I cannot teach the lesson with activities suitable for active learning and learning by doing and experiencing methods.."

When the data were analyzed, the majority of the teachers stated that the reduction of class hours to 35 minutes had no effect on the strategies, methods and techniques they used, and that they still taught the lesson with appropriate methods according to the content of the subject. On the other hand, 13 teachers stated that the decrease in the duration of the lesson caused problems in the implementation of the strategy, method or technique they determined according to the subject, and that they could not train them, so it affected them. In addition, they stated that they turned to easier, more practical activities that would not cause time problems in order to minimize the possibility of not being able to catch up due to the fact that the lesson time was less than before.

In Table 5, 'The effect of reducing class hours on students' cognitive, affective and psychomotor behaviors' is examined.

Table 5. Category-3 The Effect of Reducing Lesson Hours on Cognitive, Affective, Psychomotor Behaviours of Students

Codes	Participants-Frequency	Quote
Caution	Ö3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,12,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,22,24,27,29,30,31,34 (23)	Ö16- " They can listen to the subject to be learnt in the lesson without being distracted and do activities."
Interest	Ö3,4,7,10,12,13,14,15,16,17,19,20,21,23, 26,27,28,29,30,31,34,35 (22)	Ö20 - " Students' interest, attitude and motivation increased"
Concern	Ö2,5,8,11,18,22,24,25,32,33 (10)	Ö24- " Students are worried about not understanding the subject in a short time."
Learning difficulties	Ö1,11,13,21,23,25,26,33 (8)	Ö21 - " Some activities cannot be done because of shorter class hours, which makes learning more difficult.'
	Ö6,12,14,16,17,23 (6)	

In the table where student behaviors in cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains were examined, it was observed by the teachers that students' attention and perception towards the lesson increased with the reduction of the lesson duration to 35 minutes. According to the teachers' opinions, the shortening of the lesson time also positively affected the interest and motivation towards the lesson. It was also mentioned that the short duration of the lesson caused students to worry about understanding the subject and made it difficult to learn. They also stated that students were less physically tired during the lesson, which increased their performance in the lesson.

In Table 6, 'Situations experienced with the reduction of class hours to 35 minutes' are analyzed.

Table 6. Category-4 Situations Experienced with the Reduction of Class Hours to 35 Minutes

Codes	Participants-Frequency	Quote
Focusing	Ö2,4,5,9,11,13,15,16,17,20,22,23,25,26,27,31,34 (17)	Ö27- "Less class hours had a positive effect on students' focus and motivation."
Motivation	Ö5,7,8,10,12,14,15,19,25,26,27,28,32,35(14)	Ö26- "The fact that the lessons are more productive with less tired students increases my motivation."
Out of school time	Ö6,11,12,13,17,20,21,23,26,31,34,35(12)	Ö13- "Since the time spent at school is reduced, students can spend time for sports, arts and cultural activities after school."
Failure to keep up with the subjects	Ö2,6,15,20,21,24,32,34 (8)	Ö34- "Since the training programme is very intensive, the topics are not kept up."
Interest	Ö1,3,4,12,21,24,35 (7)	Ö4- "5 minutes earlier than 40 minutes makes the lesson positive for the student and the teacher. Since it reduces the boredom rate of the students, their interest in the lesson has also increased."
School hours	Ö7,10,18,23,29 (5)	Ö29- "While the class hours were 40 minutes, the class started at 07.00. Most students were either late or sleepless for the first lesson. When the

		<i>class hours were reduced, classes started at 08.00 and these problems were not experienced."</i>
Training programme	Ö3,12,26 (3)	Ö3- <i>"Considering the simplified education programme in the new maarif model, I think that the reduced lesson hours will be even more efficient."</i>

When we look at the situations experienced with the reduction of lesson hours to 35 minutes, it is noteworthy that students focus more on the lesson and their attention span has increased. At the same time, the reduction in class hours had a significant positive impact on teacher motivation. It was emphasized that students could direct themselves to social, artistic or sportive areas with more time to use outside of school. There are teacher opinions stating that the reduction of class hours to 35 minutes has a negative effect on the completion of the subjects. They stated that there was an increase in students' interest in the lesson and that it was beneficial to have more convenient arrival and departure times to school with the shortening of class hours. They also stated that these lesson hours are sufficient according to the simplified curriculum specified in the education model.

In Table 7, the findings of the category 'What kind of change should be made in the course hours' are analyzed.

Table 7. Category-5 What kind of a change should be made in lesson hours?

<i>Codes</i>	<i>Participants-Frequency</i>	<i>Quote</i>
35 minutes	Ö1,2,3,4,5,7,8,10,12,13,14,15,16, 17,19,20,22,23,24,26,27,28, 29,33,35 (25)	Ö1- <i>"35 minutes is quite enough. When it is longer, students get distracted and bored."</i>
40 minutes	Ö6,9,11,18,21,25,30,31,32,34 (10)	Ö34- <i>"I find it right that the lesson hours should be 40 minutes. More than that causes students to be distracted. If it is shorter, students cannot learn the subjects in depth."</i>

When asked what kind of change should be made to the lesson hours, the majority of the teachers who responded that 35 minutes, which was applied this year, was appropriate. Teachers who want it to remain 40 minutes argue that 40 minutes is ideal because there are problems in keeping up with the subjects. Since there were no participants who answered that it should be over 40 minutes, in other words, it should be increased, this option was not included in the table.

DISCUSSION

This study, which includes the opinions of teachers about the reduction of the duration of the course hours, examined the changes observed in the cognitive, affective and psychomotor areas of the students with the reduction of the course duration to 35 minutes, and the advantages and disadvantages of the duration in general. The research questions were analyzed by transforming them into five different categories.

The participants were asked the question "What should be considered when determining the course hours?" and they answered as the age of the student, attention span, intensity of the curriculum, school entrance-times, dual-single education status, and transportation facilities of the school. There are studies supporting these results in the literature. Aktay et al. (2019) argued that dual education is disadvantageous for students due to issues such as students going to school too early in the morning or leaving school too late, creating insomnia problems in the morning, or students having difficulty getting to and from school in adverse weather conditions. Similarly, in this study, it was stated that situations such as school entry and exit times being too early or too late, and the transportation possibilities of the location of the school create disadvantages for students and that these situations should be prioritized when determining the duration of the lessons.

When the effect of the reduction in class hours on the strategies, methods and techniques used in the lesson was examined, the majority of the teachers stated that the reduction in class hours to 35 minutes had no effect on the methods and techniques used, some of them stated that the strategies, methods and techniques to be used were not preferred due to the lack of time or the possibility that they would not be used, and some of them stated that practical activities that would take less time were preferred. Looking at previous studies on this subject, Karweit (1987) stated that when the time spent in school is evaluated, only 28% to 56% of it is allocated to learning activities. In this case, it can be concluded that the reduction of lessons to 35 minutes does not affect teaching activities.

When the teachers were asked about the effects of reducing the class hours on the cognitive, affective and psychomotor behaviors of the students, they stated that; attention and perceptions are clearer, interest and motivation towards the lesson increases, it creates anxiety about understanding the subject, it makes learning more difficult and physical fatigue decreases due to the short duration. Based on these views, Aydın (2000) stated that the current conditions and needs of the student have an effect on the attention process. In addition, teachers stated that while the reduction of class hours decreases socialization within the school, students tend to engage in more social and sportive activities because it increases the time outside the school, and this situation contributes positively to socialization outside the school. In the study conducted by Karakoç (2024), the relationship between high school students' perspectives on extracurricular sports activities and their socialization levels was examined. According to the findings, it was determined that students who approached sportive activities positively had higher skills in establishing and maintaining social relationships.

In response to the question of what kind of change should be made in the course hours, 71.42% of the teachers stated that it should continue to be 35 minutes, while 28.58% stated that it should remain 40 minutes. There is no teacher's opinion that the duration of the lesson should be more than 40 minutes. This data obtained from the research is in line with Çaycı (2018)'s suggestion that the lesson duration of 40 minutes should be increased. In addition, the course duration determined for the first grade level of primary school should be different from the duration determined for other grades'. As a result of this research, there was no statement that there should be more than 40 minutes of class time; at the same time, although 40% of the participants were classroom teachers, there was no opinion that a different duration should be applied for first graders.

CONCLUSION

When the results of the research are analyzed, it is seen that the participants were able to compare both situations transparently since they had 40 minutes of lectures last year and 35 minutes this year. The majority of them (71.42%) supported the 35-minute lessons. When we look at their opinions, they stated that the duration fits the simplified curriculum, that the entrance-exit times are in a range that does not threaten the safety of the students, that students are prevented from getting bored in the lesson by reducing the duration to 35 minutes, and that their attention span is used more efficiently. At the same time, they also stated that since the students' time at school was reduced, they

could spend time for out-of-school activities. Teachers also reported that this had a positive effect on their own motivation. They also think that there is not enough time for some courses, that some subjects are not completed, and that the school environment is also a socializing environment for students, so reducing the time spent at school would have a negative impact on their socialization.

SUGGESTIONS

In the research, there are teachers' opinions based on the fact that the reduction of class hours and thus the decrease in the time students spend at school will have a negative impact on the socialization of students. In order to prevent this situation, it would be beneficial to give some of the time taken from classes to breaks for students to socialize and rest. National pilots should be conducted to measure the effects of different lesson duration practices on student achievement, social development and teacher performance, and educational policies should be shaped according to these results. Curriculum developers should develop a program that is appropriate for the duration; if the class time is reduced to 35 minutes, a simplified and modular program should be prepared with appropriate outcomes, activity duration and evaluation methods. School administrators should consider stakeholder feedback mechanisms; regular feedback from teachers, students and parents on the implementation of class time can be obtained and flexible solutions can be developed within the school for the difficulties encountered in practice. In future studies on the time allocated for teaching, it would be useful for researchers to evaluate the reduced lesson time according to the opinions of students and parents.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION

The author contributed to the conceptual framework, planning, data collection, data analysis, content creation, review of findings, drafting and editing of the manuscript.

REFERENCES

- Abadzi, H. (2007). *Absenteeism and beyond: Instructional time loss and consequences* (Policy Research Working Paper No. 4376). The World Bank.
- Aktay, S., Arat, R., & Atalay, M. (2019). How much recess time should be in primary schools. In III. International Unlimited Education and Research Symposium (*USEAS 2019*) full text proceedings (ss. 754-759). Muğla.
- Arı, A., & A, V. (2004). Teachers' views on summer holiday learning loss. *Journal of National Education*, 163, 91-103.
- Aydın, A. (2000). *Development and learning psychology*. Alpha Publications.
- Camuzcu, S. (2007). *Comparison of the general achievement of first level students in regular (full day) and dual (half day) primary schools (The Case of Gaziantep Province)* (Unpublished Master Thesis). Gaziantep University, Institute of Social Sciences, Gaziantep, Turkey.
- Çaycı, B. (2018). Evaluation of course duration and course hours in primary schools according to the opinions of classroom teachers. *International Journal of Eurasian Education and Culture*, 3(5), 117-131.
- Gall, M. D., Gall, J. P., Jacobsen, D. R., & Bullock, T. L. (1990). *Tools for learning: A guide to teaching study skills*. Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED320126.pdf>
- Gökçe, F., & F, G. (2012). Teachers' and parents' views on the time students spend at school, lesson and rest periods, holidays and school terms. *Educational Sciences in Theory and Practice*, 12(4), 2541-2560.
- İCESTurkey. *The Finnish education system and the secrets of success*. <https://www.icesturkey.com/finlandiya-egitim-sistemi-ve-basarisinin-sirlari>
- Karweit, N. (1987). *Full or half-day kindergarten: Does it matter?* Center for Research on Elementary and Middle Schools.

What is this. (2022, January 15). What is the French education system, briefly?. <https://www.nedir-bu.com/fransaegitimsisteminedirkisaca2022/#:~:text=Fransa'da%20y%C4%B1l%C4%B1k%20e%C4%9Fitim%20s%C3%BCresi,55%20dakika%20olarak%20e%C4%9Fitim%20verilmektedir>

OECD. (2016a). *Education at a glance 2016: OECD indicators*. <http://www.oecd.org/edu/education-at-a-glance-19991487.htm>

OECD. (2016b). *PISA 2015 results (Volume I): Excellence and equity in education*. PISA, OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264266490-en>

Sağlam, M. (1999). *Education system of European countries*. Anadolu University Publications.

Tabak, H., & Şahin, F. (2020). Observation of one lesson time in secondary education institutions. *Turkish Journal of Educational Sciences*, 18(2), 123-135.

Board of Education. (2023, September 14). *Weekly course schedules*. Ministry of National Education. <https://ttkb.meb.gov.tr/www/haftalik-ders-cizelgeleri/kategori/7>

Tazebay, A., Çelenk, S., Tertemiz, N., & Kalaycı, N. (2000). *Primary education programmes and developments*. Nobel Publication Distribution.

Usul, A. S. (2019, May 2). *Students' dreams: Reduction of compulsory teaching hours*. Anadolu Agency. <https://www.aa.com.tr/tr/egitim/ogrencilerin-hayali-zorunlu-ders-saatlerinin-azaltilmasi/1432233>

Yıldırım, A., & Şimşek, H. (2006). *Qualitative research methods in social sciences*. Seçkin Publishing.

Study Abroad. *Overview of the education system in the UK*. <https://www.yurtdisiegitim.net/ingilterede-egitim-sistemine-genel-bakis/>